

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

Grant Agreement No. 101036756

Update on EU policy initiatives contributing to the prevention, prioritisation and removal of persistent and mobile substances in 2025

Work Package 3 – Policy analysis, development, and assessment

January 2026

Initiatives adopted in 2025

Legislative procedures

Adoption of the Soil Monitoring Directive

The [Soil Monitoring Directive](#) was published in the Official Journal in November 2025 and entered into force on 16 December 2025. The Directive establishes the first EU-wide framework requiring Member States to monitor and assess soil health using common descriptors. To gather data on soil contamination, Member States are required to establish a list of soil contaminants including pesticides, their metabolites and PFAS. The Commission is also mandated to adopt by 17 June 2027, an indicative list of high-risk contaminants, including PFAS and pesticides, for which further data is needed. Member States will monitor the selected PFAS (PFAS-21, PFAS-43, or their own selection in their national list) and selected pesticides and metabolites, although, to limit the monitoring costs, Member States are allowed to perform measurements only on a limited number of sampling points. Member States are required to report their monitoring data for the first time by June 2032 and every six years after that date.

The Soil Monitoring Directive also provides for a common approach on the identification and management of contaminated sites. Member States must identify all potentially contaminated sites existing on or before 16 December 2025 by December 2035. Once identified and registered, potentially contaminated sites then undergo soil investigations to confirm contamination, and if contamination is confirmed, site-specific risk assessments to evaluate risks to health and the environment. Member State individually define what constitutes an unacceptable risk for human health and the environment. Member States are required to take appropriate risk reduction measures

‘without undue delay’ (no other timeline is provided in the Directive). Member States must also set up a public register of contaminated and potentially contaminated sites by December 2029.

Adoption of the One Substance, One Assessment package, including a Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals

The ‘One substance, one assessment package’ was published in the Official Journal on 12 December 2025 and entered into force on 1 January 2026. The Package contains [Regulation \(EU\) 2025/2455 establishing a common data platform on chemicals](#) and a Regulation and a Directive amending several existing legal acts with the aim of streamlining risk assessment tasks and improving cooperation across EU agencies.

The common data platform on chemicals, to be set up by ECHA by January 2029, aims to support EU chemicals legislation and policy by centralising chemicals-related information in one place and making it findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). The platform will host ‘chemicals data’, defined broadly as including “information on physicochemical properties, hazard properties, use, exposure, risk, occurrence, emissions, fate and manufacturing process of chemicals, as well as environmental sustainability-related information on chemicals, including climate change-related information, regulatory process-related information on chemicals, data on alternatives to substances of concern, standard formats, controlled vocabularies, or any information on applicable legal obligations relating to chemicals” (Article 2(10)). The platform will draw on data generated under various EU legislation, EU, national and international research programmes and voluntary contributions from Member States, agencies, research institutes and third-country organisations. The platform will be organised into several services: a) IPCHEM, b) a repository of reference values adopted under EU legislation, c) a database of study notifications, d) a database containing information on regulatory processes, e) a database containing data on chemicals in articles or products, f) a database containing data on alternatives to substances of concern, g) a database containing information on obligations under Union chemicals legislation, h) a repository of standard formats and controlled vocabularies, and i) a database on environmental sustainability-related data. The Regulation also tasks the EEA to establish an early warning system for emerging chemical risks, by 2 January 2027, aggregating signals from various sources (including data from EU agencies and national early warning systems).

The Regulation tasks the EEA and ECHA with the creation of a framework of indicators to monitor chemical pollution throughout a chemical’s lifecycle (emissions, occurrence and fate) and the drivers and impacts of exposure to chemicals, and to measure the effectiveness of chemicals legislation and the transition towards the production of safe and sustainable chemicals. The framework will include, to the extent possible, ‘an aggregated territory-based risk indicator’ to monitor time and spatial trends in exposure of populations to chemicals and associated health risks. The framework of indicators will be accessible in the form of an indicator dashboard made available through the common data platform. The Regulation also tasks ECHA and EFSA, in cooperation with the EEA, to commission a Union-wide human biomonitoring study covering all Member States by January 2030.

Adoption of PFAS ban in toys in Toy Safety Regulation

The [Toy Safety Regulation](#) (repealing the former Toy Safety Directive) was published in the Official Journal on 12 December 2025 and entered into force on 1 January 2026. The Regulation will apply from 1 August 2030. The Regulation prohibits the intentional use of PFAS (defined according to the OECD definition) in toys, components of toys or micro-structurally distinct parts of toys. The prohibition does not apply to batteries in toys and toy components necessary for electronic or electric functions of the toy if the substance is full inaccessible.

The Regulation also extends generic prohibitions based on CLP classification, which already existed for CMRs in the previous Directive, to endocrine disruptors for human health category 1 or 2; substances toxic to a specific target organ category 1 (single or repeated exposure), respiratory sensitisers category 1, to which were added in the final text skin sensitisers 1A. Proposals from the Parliament to add to this list endocrine disruptors for the environment, PMT/vPvM and PBT/vPvB were not maintained in the final Regulation. Exemptions to generic prohibitions and to the PFAS prohibition may be granted by the Commission following safety and alternative assessments by ECHA.

Provisional agreement reached on the revision of the water legislation, including PFAS surface and groundwater standards

The provisional agreement on the revision of the Water Framework Directive, the Groundwater Directive and the Environmental Quality Standards Directive was reached by co-legislators on 23 September 2025. To be adopted, the text still needs a positive vote in the Council and in the European Parliament's plenary (planned for March 2026). The main changes include:

- ▼ **PFAS and TFA:** a surface water quality standard is created for the sum of 25 PFAS (Sum of 24 PFAS from the original Commission proposal + TFA) - 0,0044 µg/L in water and 0,077 µg/L in biota. The groundwater parameter for the Sum of PFAS is aligned with the Drinking Water Directive (PFAS 20 0,10 µg/L) and a quality standard for the Sum of 4 PFAS is created (0,0044 µg/L). In the next review of quality standards, the Commission should consider establishing quality standards for PFAS Total and TFA (separately) in surface waters and groundwater. The Commission is also tasked with supplementing the guidance on monitoring PFAS Total to cover surface and groundwater.
- ▼ **Pesticides:** a surface water quality standard is created for the 'Sum of active substances in pesticides' for which an EQS is set in the Directive (0.2 µg/L). In the next review of quality standards, the Commission should consider the possible inclusion of a surface water quality standard for the 'Sum of selected pesticides by 'mode of action''. A new groundwater quality standard is created for non-relevant metabolite of pesticides. Within two years of the entry into force of the Directive, the Commission must adopt a list of known pesticide metabolites indicating which are relevant and non-relevant (and update it every 6 years). In the next review of groundwater quality standards, the Commission should

consider whether to revise the quality standards pesticides (individual and total) and for non-relevant metabolites.

- ▼ **Pharmaceuticals:** At the next review of the surface and groundwater quality standards, the Commission should consider the introduction of a quality standard for the ‘sum of selected pharmaceuticals by mode of action’ in surface and groundwater.
- ▼ **Application and review of quality standards:** new quality standards will take effect from 22 December 2027, with the aim of achieving good surface water chemical status in relation to those substances by 22 December 2039. The Commission is tasked with reviewing the surface and groundwater quality standards every six years and, where appropriate, to issue a legislative proposal for the revision of the standards. ECHA is tasked to prepare scientific reports to support the review, including proposals for quality standards or threshold values and analytical methods.
- ▼ **Surface and groundwater watchlists** have to be established two years after the entry into force of the Directive and then updated every three years. The groundwater watchlist is capped to five substances, the surface water watchlist at ten substances. Member States have to monitor each substance on the watchlists over a 24-month period. ECHA is tasked to prepare scientific reports to support the review of the watchlists, which will contain a list of candidate substances and indicative analysis methods and maximum acceptable limits of quantification for each substance.
- ▼ **Joint monitoring facility:** the agreement tasks the Commission with publishing within 18 months of the entry into force of the Directive a report on options for the establishment, financing and functioning of a joint European monitoring facility and if appropriate, to put forward a legislative proposal in order to establish it.
- ▼ **Extended producer responsibility:** the agreement tasks the Commission to publish a report within three years on the possibility to include an extended producer responsibility mechanism in the Water Framework Directive. The report should evaluate the feasibility of requiring producers that place on the EU market products containing any of the substances that have an EQS or a groundwater quality standard to contribute to the costs of monitoring programmes.

Delegated and implementing acts

Adoption of the restriction of PFAS in firefighting foams

The [REACH restriction on PFAS in firefighting foams](#) was adopted on 3 October by the Commission and entered into force on 23 October 2025. The restriction sets a maximum concentration of 1 mg/L for the sum of all PFAS in firefighting foams. The restriction provides a ten-year transition period for firefighting foams used in installations belonging to the offshore oil and gas industry, military vessels, civilian ships, industrial sites covered by the Seveso Directive. Transitional periods are also provided for the use of firefighting foams containing PFAS above the set threshold in public fire services (18

months) and portable fire extinguishers (31 December 2030). The restriction also sets out labelling requirements applicable to fighting foams containing PFAS above the set threshold and to the stock of not-utilised firefighting foams and PFAS-containing waste.

Revised surface water watchlist includes new PMT/vPvM substances

The Commission adopted the [fifth watchlist of substances in surface waters](#) suspected of posing a risk to the environment and human health on 28 February 2025. The surface watchlist mechanism was established in 2013 to improve the available information on substances of concern. Member States have to monitor the substances on the list at least once per year for up to four years. The new watchlist contains twelve chemicals or groups of chemicals. Among the new substances included in the list are several PMT/vPvM substances or precursors of PMT/vPvM substances: 6PPD-quinone (CAS no. 2754428-18-5); 10 azole fungicides, including in particular bromuconazole (CAS no. 116255-48-2), climbazole (CAS no. 38083-17-9), difenoconazole (CAS no. 119446-68-3), mefentrifluconazole (CAS no. 1417782-03-6), and triticonazole (CAS no. 131983-72-7) and TFA precursor Fluoxetine (CAS no. 54910-89-3).

Communications and strategies

European Water Resilience Strategy

The European Commission published the [European Water Resilience Strategy](#) on 4 June 2025. The Strategy sets an overall water efficiency goal of ‘enhancing water efficiency by at least 10% by 2030’ by reducing demand, over-abstraction and improving efficiency across sectors. The Strategy however leaves the development of a methodology to set water efficiency targets to future work with Member States and stakeholders and the establishment of common targets to the review of the strategy in 2027.

Regarding water pollution, the Strategy recognises that ‘Water quality and quantity are two sides of the same coin’ and that Europe ‘must continue working on preventing pollution at source’. It also states that ‘urgent action is needed to tackle pollutants which pose a risk to our vital sources of drinking water’ including highly persistent pollutants such as PFAS and claims that ‘the EU must take decisive efforts to clean up sites already strongly polluted by these, and other, ubiquitous, persistent, bio-accumulative and toxic substances’. In terms of planned actions, the main initiatives listed in the Strategy concern increasing efforts to better implement EU water legislation in the Member States and funding for remediation. The Commission announces the establishment of a ‘public-private initiative to achieve a technological breakthrough in feasible and affordable methods for the detection and remediation of PFAS and other persistent chemicals’, with the caution that the right financial partners must be found first to launch the initiative. Regarding funding, the Strategy also announces further cooperation between the Commission and the European Investment Bank to deploy water investments.

Regulatory initiatives and implementation milestones in 2026

Q1 2026

EU PFAS drinking water parameters become applicable in all Member States

The drinking water parameters for the Sum of 20 individual PFAS (0.1 µg/L) and Total PFAS (0.5 µg/L), introduced in the Drinking Water Directive in 2020, become applicable on 12 January 2026 (i.e. the parameters must be monitored and actions taken if they are exceeded).

General PFAS restriction – consultation on SEAC draft opinion

The 60-day consultation on the draft opinion of the Committee for Socio-Economic Analysis (SEAC) on the PFAS restriction proposal is expected to start in March 2026.

Revision of Annex II of the Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation

According to Article 15 of the Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation, the Commission was expected to adopt by 31 December 2025, a delegated act reviewing the list of substances and thresholds set out in Annex II to the Regulation. The procedure is ongoing; the Commission presented a draft delegated act to the expert group in October 2025. The Commission is also expected to publish guidelines on reporting procedures, ‘including technical guidelines regarding methods facilitating analysis for monitoring of PFAS’ in January 2026 (Article 13).

Adoption of the ‘pharma package’

The ‘pharma package’ contains a proposal for a new Directive on the Union code relating to medicinal products for human use and a new Regulation on Union procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human use. A provisional agreement has been reached between the Council and the European Parliament on 11 December 2025. The text must now formally be approved by both institutions.

Commission Roadmap to phase out animal testing in chemical safety assessments

The European Commission is preparing a roadmap outlining actions ‘to further reduce and ultimately phase out animal testing under all relevant pieces of chemical legislation (e.g. REACH, Biocidal Product Regulation, Plant Protection Products Regulation and human and veterinary medicines)’. The roadmap should in particular set out a ‘path to expanding and accelerating the development, validation and implementation of non-animal methods as well as means to facilitate their uptake across legislation’. The Roadmap is expected to be released in Q1 2026.

Implementation guidance for the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)

The Commission indicated in the [Communication](#) accompanying the Environmental Omnibus it would issue ‘as a priority’ an implementation guidance on the recently adopted PPWR, which will cover PFAS testing methods.

Q2 2026

Adoption of the Directive amending the water legislation

As indicated above, the provisional agreement on the revision of the Water Framework Directive, the Groundwater Directive and the Environmental Quality Standards Directive was reached on 23 September 2025. The Council and the Parliament should formally adopt the Directive in Q1 2026 (Parliament's plenary currently scheduled for March). The Directive will then be published in the Official Journal and enter into force likely in Q2 2026.

PMT/vPvM classification and labelling requirements become applicable for new mixtures

From 1 May 2026, mixtures placed on the market as of 1 May 2026 must be classified and labelled in accordance with PMT/vPvM hazard classes. For mixtures placed on the market before 1 May 2026, classification and labelling will become mandatory from 1 May 2028.

Commission proposal for a revision of the Water Framework Directive

In the [RESourceEU Action Plan](#) to accelerate efforts to secure the EU's supply of critical raw materials, adopted on 3 December 2025, the European Commission announced a revision of the Water Framework Directive for Q2 2025. This was confirmed by the publication of the [Communication](#) accompanying the Environmental Omnibus on 10 December 2025. The exact content of the revision is not specified in these documents, but the focus will be on simplification and addressing potential bottlenecks to promote circularity and access to critical raw materials in the EU.

Q3 2026

Adoption of governance framework and implementation plan for the common data platform on chemicals

The Commission is expected to adopt by 2 July 2026 a governance framework for the common data platform on chemicals, with the support of a steering committee, consisting of at least one representative from each of the EU Agencies and representatives of the Commission, to be set up in Q1 2026. The Commission is also expected to adopt by 2 July 2026 an implementation plan identifying datasets of chemicals data to be included in the common data platform, together with a timeline for their inclusion.

Prohibition to place on the market food-contact packaging containing PFAS enters into force

From 12 July 2026, it will no longer be permitted to place on the market food-contact packaging containing PFAS above the threshold defined in the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation.

Commission proposal for a Circular Economy Act

The Commission proposal for a Circular economy Act is expected to be released in Q3 2026. The proposed act will aim to ‘facilitate the free movement of ‘circular’ products, secondary raw materials and waste’, increase critical raw materials recovery (in particular through the revision of the Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive) and ‘stimulate demand for these materials in the EU’ (see [Have your say – Circular Economy Act](#) and [RESourceEU Action Plan](#)). According to the [Communication](#) accompanying the Environmental Omnibus on 10 December 2025, the Circular Economy Act may include ‘larger scale reform of extended producer responsibility scheme’.

Q4 2026

Final RAC and SEAC opinions on the PFAS restriction

Following the consultation on the draft SEAC opinion, which will start in March 2026, the Committee will adopt its final opinion. ECHA expects to deliver the final RAC and SEAC opinions to the European Commission by the end of 2026.

RAC opinion on the classification of TFA as PMT and vPvM substance

Germany has submitted two dossiers for revising the harmonised classification of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and adopt a new harmonised classification for sodium trifluoroacetate and other inorganic salts of trifluoroacetic acid in June 2024. New proposed hazards include PMT, vPvM and Reprotoxic 1B. The public consultation was held in May-July 2025. The RAC is expected to adopt its opinion by 17 October 2026.

PMT/vPvM classification and labelling requirements become applicable for all substances

From 1 November 2026, substances placed on the market before 1 May 2025 must be classified and labelled in accordance with PMT/vPvM hazard classes. Substances placed on the market as of 1 May 2025 already have to be classified and labelled since 1 May 2025.

ECHA to submit report on substances of concern in packaging

ECHA is expected to submit a report on the presence of substances of concern in packaging and packaging components to the Commission by 31 December 2026. This report is mandated by the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation and aims to determine the extent to which substances of concern in packaging negatively affect the re-use and recycling of materials or impact chemical safety.

Also expected in 2026:

Legislative procedure – Environmental Omnibus

The European Commission published on 10 December 2025 a [package of proposals for the simplification of administrative burdens in environmental legislation](#) (eighth ‘Omnibus’). The proposals amend a large number of legal acts on waste, industrial emissions and

environmental assessments, with a view to simplify administrative, reporting and environmental management requirements. The proposals affect in particular the Industrial Emissions Directive (IED), which had been revised in 2024. The Omnibus, among other changes, removes the obligation to have a chemical inventory in the environmental management system (EMS), and postpones the application of certain new IED requirements beyond July 2026. The proposals will undergo legislative procedure in 2026.

Legislative procedure – Food and feed simplification package

The European Commission published on 16 December 2025 a [legislative proposal](#) for a Regulation amending several EU legal acts on food and feed safety. The legislative proposal includes amendments to the Plant Protection Products Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009) making approvals of active substances unlimited in time, with the exception of active substances that are candidates for substitution and those approved by derogation because they have properties that are of concern with regards to human or animal health or the environment. The proposal however leaves the possibility to set time limits where necessary based on the risk assessment and provides for additional ad-hoc review clauses, in addition to the existing Article 21 of Regulation. The proposal will undergo legislative procedure in 2026.

Commission proposal for a revision of the REACH Regulation

Originally planned for Q4 2025, the Commission proposal for the revision of the REACH Regulation was postponed following the negative opinion from the Regulatory Scrutiny Board on the impact assessment underpinning the legislative proposal. The Commission is strengthening the impact assessment ahead of a resubmission to the Regulatory Scrutiny Board, for which a clear timeline has not been provided. In December 2025, Eric Mamer, director-general for the environment at the European Commission, [indicated](#) that the revision is expected 'early 2026'.

H2020 project Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances
EU Grant Agreement No. 101036756